

A photograph of a laboratory setting. In the foreground, a pipette with a pink handle and a yellow tip is positioned over a petri dish containing a red liquid. The petri dish is part of a multi-well tray. Other petri dishes are visible in the background, some containing blue and yellow liquids. The background is a soft, out-of-focus light blue.

erinha

European Research Infrastructure
on Highly Pathogenic Agents

Dual use in the life sciences

Briefing note

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01	16 Feb 2026	Finalisation of first version	Jonathan EWBANK

Dual use in the life sciences

Key point. “Dual use” has two main meanings. In trade/security law it refers to items, software and technology with both civilian and military applications. In the life sciences it refers to beneficial research that could also be misapplied to cause harm; “DURC” is the narrower subset where misuse would be especially plausible or severe.

1. What “dual use” means

Trade/export-control meaning

The EU uses “dual use” primarily for export-control purposes. The legal anchor is Regulation (EU) 2021/821, which governs exports, brokering, technical assistance, transit and transfer of dual-use items.

Life-science governance meaning

WHO uses the term for research conducted for peaceful purposes that could also generate knowledge, methods, products or technologies that may be intentionally misused to endanger humans, animals, plants, agriculture or the environment. “DURC” refers to the more acute subset where harmful misuse could occur with no, or only minor, modification.

2. Oversight architecture

National level

Most countries distribute oversight across ministries and institutions. Common national functions are export licensing and enforcement; biosafety and biosecurity rules for work with regulated biological agents; funding and ethics requirements; and institutional review by biosafety, research security or DURC-type committees.

EU level

The EU level is strongest on export controls, but policy is broadening. The Commission’s 2024 White Paper on dual-use R&D, the 2025 Preparedness Union Strategy (“dual-use by design”), and two 2025 expert reports (see references, below) all point toward closer integration of civil and defence R&I while safeguarding sensitive research and responsible innovation.

International level

The main international layers are UNSCR 1540, the Biological Weapons Convention, the Chemical Weapons Convention, and export-control regimes such as the Australia Group. For life-science governance, WHO’s 2022 global guidance framework is the main normative reference.

3. Practical implications for life-science policy

A useful test is whether a proposal raises mainly: (a) transfer/export questions, (b) research-governance questions, or (c) both. A pathogen-related project may require institutional risk assessment and publication review even when no export licence is implicated; conversely, materials, equipment or know-how may trigger export controls even when the science is otherwise

low-risk. Generally, there is a lack of coordinated oversight to bridge the two areas, export-control frameworks and research governance. This creates gaps in oversight, responsibility, and implementation.

4. Teaching and training resources

Priority resources already available include: WHO’s online course “Dual-use research and the responsible use of the life sciences”; WHO’s Global guidance framework; the Dutch Biosecurity Office’s Dual-Use Quicksan; and European Virus Archive materials on DURC in high-consequence virology. Training should target scientists, funders, policy makers, ethics bodies, publishers, procurement teams and export-control officials.

5. Recommendations for near-term policy actions

Clarify scope	Use distinct language for export-control dual use versus life-science dual-use research, and establish clear criteria for when enhanced oversight (e.g. DURC) should apply.
Align review	Connect biosafety, biosecurity, ethics, funding and export-control processes, including shared risk-assessment approaches and/or review pathways, so researchers are not left to navigate fragmented systems.
Anchor governance in operational practice	Ensure that dual-use governance frameworks are informed by the practical experience and operational expertise, such as that developed within specialised research infrastructures, to improve the coherence and implementability of governance approaches.
Invest in capability	Make awareness training mandatory for relevant institutions, with escalation routes for expert review and access to practical tools.
Use proportionate controls	Ensure that risk mitigation measures remain targeted and evidence-based, to avoid overly broad restrictions that chill legitimate science, while reinforcing accountability and traceability, with targeted safeguards for higher-risk activities.

Selected references

- EU dual-use technologies; [Overview](#); [EU: Regulation \(EU\) 2021/821](#); [European Commission White Paper on dual-use R&D](#) (2024); [Preparedness Union Strategy](#) (2025); [Making the most of EU Research and Innovation Investments: rethinking dual use](#) (2025); [Unlocking the potential of dual-use research and innovation](#) (2025).
- International/life sciences: [WHO Global guidance framework for the responsible use of the life sciences](#) (2022); [WHO Academy course](#); [RIVM Dual use quickscan](#); [EVA DURC life sciences guide](#); [UNSCR 1540](#); [BWC](#); [CWC](#); [Australia Group materials](#).